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Research article

LiDAR-derived high resolution vegetation structure and selection patterns of the common nightingale *Luscinia megarhynchos* in riparian habitats

Jean-Nicolas Pradervand¹✉, Florian Zellweger², Jérémy Gremion¹, Aristide Parisod¹, Bertrand Posse¹, Emmanuel Revaz¹ and Alain Jacot¹

¹Swiss Ornithological Institute, Regional Office Valais, Sion, Switzerland

²Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research, WSL, Birmensdorf, Switzerland

Correspondence: Jean-Nicolas Pradervand (jean-nicolas.pradervand@vogelwarte.ch)

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Human-induced alterations in natural water flow have seriously impaired the integrity of riverine ecosystems. Nonetheless, even in human-altered riverine and adjacent terrestrial habitats, there is considerable potential for the protection of rare species if management practices prioritize biodiversity conservation. However, the management of such areas often presents complex challenges. On the one hand, efforts to mitigate natural hazards frequently overshadow biodiversity conservation objectives. On the other hand, high-resolution maps of forest structures are often lacking but could be very useful for spatial prioritization of conservation efforts, especially as vegetation structure can be directly managed through local restoration activities. Here, we used an airborne LiDAR-derived vegetation structure along an 80 km stretch of the Rhône River (Valais, Switzerland) to assess the habitat characteristics that best explain the presence of a flagship species, the common nightingale *Luscinia megarhynchos*, a species that historically thrived along this river system but has experienced a drastic population decline over the past decades. Nightingales showed a preference for dense vegetation in the lower strata above ground (3–6 m), as opposed to an open and sparsely vegetated ground level (0–1 m). The preferred habitats were predominantly located within forested regions, as indicated by a preference for taller canopies. These findings align surprisingly well with prior field research on the species, demonstrating the capability of high-resolution LiDAR to upscale locally derived habitat preferences across very large areas. Based on LiDAR outputs, we proposed management recommendations for the whole river. Such spatially detailed information furthers our understanding of local habitat preferences of endangered species, thus facilitating the formulation of conservation recommendations at the scale of entire populations.

Keywords: habitat preference, LiDAR, nightingale, riparian habitat

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Introduction

River ecosystems are under high pressure as human activities have led to dramatic changes in natural flow regimes (Allan 2004). This is particularly true for the construction of longitudinal dams along channelized rivers, mainly to ensure safety through measures such as flood control and to reclaim land for agricultural use. Such measures lead to the degradation of healthy river ecosystems, negatively impacting habitat diversity and biodiversity in the riverbed by altering sediment transportation and deposition (Nilsson and Dynesius 1994, Poff et al. 1997), but also in the adjacent riparian habitats (Arlettaz et al. 2011). The interface between a naturally flowing river and the land often provides a mosaic of habitats that can act as vital and large-scale connectors between fragmented habitat types and provide multiple ecosystem services (Riis et al. 2020). Therefore, its conservation and restoration should be a high priority when determining the needs of river ecosystems and their management. Restored fluvial and riverine ecosystems have the potential to support rare species, contingent upon appropriate management practices that prioritize biodiversity (Naiman et al. 1993, Arlettaz et al. 2011, Décamps 2011).

Riparian habitats are often the last semi-natural elements crossing anthropogenized landscapes, either in agricultural (Almeida et al. 2021) or urbanized (Keten et al. 2020) landscapes. They serve as vital breeding grounds and connectors for species that prefer not to cross open habitats, as evidenced by numerous studies on birds (Gillies and St. Clair 2008, Şekercioglu et al. 2015) or mammals (Clements et al. 2011, Yaap et al. 2016). These corridors are crucial for supporting animal movement and preserving regional biodiversity (Naiman et al. 1993). In addition to favoring common species, especially near settlements or urbanized areas (Keten et al. 2020), these corridors are also used by endangered species to migrate through, rest, or even breed (Bennett et al. 2014). While rivers have been proposed as priority objects for ecological networks in Switzerland, the quality of these riparian corridors varies greatly depending on their condition (from natural to dammed, and depending on the surrounding vegetation; Kinley and Newhouse 1997, Hagar 1999). The need for large-scale methodological approaches that allow quantifying fine-scale variation in habitat characteristics within a mosaic of habitat types is particularly relevant in such a context.

LiDAR (light detection and ranging) is a remote sensing technology that captures detailed information about 3D habitat structure (Davies and Asner 2014), and is thus particularly useful for assessing avian habitat preferences related to vegetation structure (Goetz et al. 2010, Vogeler et al. 2013, Zellweger et al. 2013). LiDAR has spurred research on species–habitat relationships at large scales, as evidenced by studies on various animals and plants in different forest types (Engler et al. 2013, Tweedy et al. 2019, Hagar et al. 2020, Blouin et al. 2021, Warner et al. 2022). At smaller scales, LiDAR has been used to understand bird responses related to the vegetation structure for single species (Bakx et al. 2019, Turner et al. 2023) and also for bird diversity (Clawges et al.

2008, Sasaki et al. 2016). However, most studies often reduce the LiDAR data to pixels, limiting the use of the datasets to 2D models (Bakx et al. 2019). For many species, habitat structure proves more critical than single measures such as tree height or canopy information, as shown in *Paridae* or fairy-wrens, whose abundance or nest location was best predicted by using the density of points in 3D-voxels (corresponding to the density of the vegetation; Sasaki et al. 2016, Turner et al. 2023). These findings demonstrate the importance of LiDAR to understand complex, three-dimensional relationships, even when targeting only one type of forest (i.e. dense forests in the case of the *Paridae*), and to improve knowledge of single- or multiple-species habitat selection and preference patterns using complex structural traits (Valbuena et al. 2020, Lenoir et al. 2022).

In this study, we used LiDAR to precisely depict the habitat of a bird living in riparian habitats along the Rhône River, which is currently going through an important restructuring process. Among the bird species using forested areas with specific tree species and vegetation structures, the common nightingale *Luscinia megarhynchos* (hereafter referred to as ‘nightingale’) is of particular interest in this study. This species, showing a large distribution in Europe (Keller et al. 2020) and Switzerland, is locally declining due to inappropriate river management, especially after river canalization and damming (Arlettaz et al. 2019). Nightingales are often associated with riparian areas and need specific vegetation structures to hide and feed (Stuttard and Williamson 1971, Wilson et al. 2005, Allen et al. 2012, Holt et al. 2012). Detailed field studies have demonstrated that nightingales select territories with a higher proportion of bare ground and short vegetation below the canopy of trees in areas densely covered by bushes (Wilson et al. 2005). Over large areas, such fine-scaled vegetation characteristics are difficult to assess, but LiDAR potentially offers the opportunity for a large-scale, cost-effective, and observer-independent assessment. Using this large-scale approach would ask the following questions: 1) can we infer significant, meaningful vegetation characteristics for the nightingale based on LiDAR data? 2) Do we achieve similar results to small-scale field studies on habitat preferences of the nightingale using LiDAR? 3) What is the potential of the LiDAR approach for fine-scale habitat suitability models?

Material and methods

Study area

This study focuses on the adjacent habitats along the Rhône River between Lake Léman (46°23'41"N, 6°51'32"E, also called Lake Geneva) and the city of Sierre (46°16'57"N, 7°32'30"E), a stretch roughly 80 km in length. The Rhône River takes its source from the Rhône glacier in the middle of the Swiss Alps. This cold alluvial river flows in the bottom of the Valais valley. The part of the river between Sierre and the lake experienced two major corrections that affected its riparian habitats. The first correction happened between 1863

and 1894, when small groins were created perpendicularly to the river to concentrate the flow in the axis of the river. A second correction took place between 1936 and 1961. Here, longitudinal dams were constructed to deal with seasonal floods, mainly from snow melts in late spring. This totally changed the aspect of the river towards a linear and flat riverbed boarded by stone walls to avoid erosion. The riverbanks have been transformed into elevated embankments alongside each side of the river, typically accompanied by a concrete pathway at the summit of these structures. The interior and exterior dam sides are partially covered with ligneous vegetation, depending on the local management. Some areas are covered by forests or tree patches, while others feature small patches of bushes or herbaceous vegetation. Nearly all of the riverbanks are dammed, significantly limiting the available area for biodiversity.

Bird data collection

Fifty percent of all available nightingale data from the canton of Valais are within 151 m of the Rhône River, and 70% within 268 m (Swiss Ornithological Institute database, <https://www.vogelwarte.ch/fr/recherche/monitoring/dispositio-n-des-donnees/>, extract of all data from 2000 to 2022 – note that the bird data coverage in the valley bottom is relatively high and covers all nightingale hotspots). Our study focuses on these riverbanks, which provide the main breeding habitat of the nightingale in Valais and where the biggest flood protection project in Switzerland is now taking place. We collected bird data along well-defined transects on both sides of the dams between 15 April and 15 June 2016, following the methods of the national common breeding bird monitoring scheme in Switzerland (Schmid et al. 2004). This standardized method consists of three rounds of surveys per transect, starting at dawn and ending before 11:00. The starting point was always alternated between surveys of the same transect, and sampling effort (walking speed) was kept constant irrespective of habitat and bird abundance. The transect monitoring protocol consists of walking at a regular speed along the transect, recording all the birds seen or heard. The 180 km of river banks were split into 14 transects of a maximum of 12 km. For each bird contacted, we recorded in the field its exact GPS position based on high-resolution aerial photographs. As we worked along transects (river dams) of small width, locating the birds was relatively easy and allowed an estimation (visually or by localization of the sound) of the height above the ground of the nightingale when it was first detected. A total of 253 height estimations were collected, of which 224 measurements fell within the range of 0–3 m. The bias due to inaccurate height estimates is likely to be low for this range. The width of the vegetation patch (perpendicularly to the vegetation corridor) in which a bird was detected was estimated using high-resolution aerial photographs (Supporting information).

LiDAR data

To quantify the structure of the vegetation homogeneously along the whole transect of the river banks we used a LiDAR

(light detection and ranging) approach. A helicopter equipped with a LiDAR system (Helimap system) flew at an altitude of 230 m above the two river dams on 20 April 2016 at the start of bud burst of many tree species (Spring Index; <https://www.meteoswiss.admin.ch/climate/climate-change/vegetation-development/spring-index.html>). The spring index indicates the difference in yearly vegetation phenology compared to the averaged period 1991–2020. The LiDAR system covered a band with an average width of 250 m per trip, resulting in a point density of 140 pts/m². This density of points allows a deep sampling of the lower vegetation strata and, consequently, a high raster resolution of the different LiDAR products (Bakx et al. 2019).

The point cloud was then cleaned (removal of buildings, power lines, bridges), normalized according to the ratio of points reaching the different strata and the total amount of points per m², and used to generate a digital elevation model (DEM), as well as a digital surface model (DSM), both at 1 m resolution. Canopy height was calculated by subtracting the DEM from the DSM, indicative of vegetation height above ground. This resulted in values from 0 (no woody vegetation above ground) to 20 (trees reaching a max height of 20 m above ground). Based on the cloud of points, we calculated a third type of layer: the proportional point density for each cubic meter of the area (from the ground to 20 m). This layer provides the density of the vegetation for each 1 × 1 × 1 m³ pixel. Then, we separated this information in 20 strata (from 0 m – ground level – to 20 m) containing the information on vegetation density for each 1 m step at a resolution of 1 m³. Reaching the maximal height of the data (above 20 m) would result in outliers and drastically reduce the number of presence points, strongly impacting the uncertainty of the results (i.e. only 11.8% of nightingale presences left at 22 m, 8.2% at 24 m). These density layers indicate the relative point density per cubic meter (these cubic meters are hereafter referred to as voxels) and correspond to the density of the vegetation. The vegetation has also been classified according to canopy data as open vegetation (0–1 m), bushy vegetation (1–3 m), young stands (3–6 m), and old stands (> 6 m).

Data extraction

Using the different LiDAR layers, we extracted vegetation density and canopy cover for all the nightingale presence data points, extracting the median of the surrounding voxels in a radius of 1.5 m to allow for incertitude in bird localization. Among 357 presence data, 347 were included in the processed LiDAR data (i.e. 10 were excluded when processing the LiDAR because they were under objects like power lines, bridges, etc., and were discarded). For each presence point, we randomly set 12 absence points within a radius of 25 m from the observation point of the nightingale. This radius was used in several fine-scale habitat studies in passerines, like the white-winged snowfinches (Resano-Mayor et al. 2019) or Dupont's lark (Pérez-Granados et al. 2017). The selected radius of 25 m allowed us to keep the control point in similar vegetation patches and thus understand fine-scale preferences of nightingales. These absence points had to fall within

vegetation structures (no human settlements, roads, or power lines), not in open vegetation like grasslands or pastures, and at a minimum of 3 m between them. Among these, 3739 absence points (out of 4164; 12×347) filled these criteria, and for each of them we used the same 1.5 m radius to extract the median of the vegetation density for each stratum. This corresponds to a total of 3–12 absence points for each presence point (minimum = 3, maximum = 12, average = 10.5).

To understand these preferences, we compared the density of vegetation between presence and absence points (median on 1.5 m radius) for the different vegetation strata. As we work in three dimensions, each stratum shows a different number of presences and absences. Indeed, while ground observations encompass the entirety of the dataset, the number of data points significantly diminishes as one ascends through the strata and breaks above the canopy. This leads to zeros in the analysis, which should not be considered. The dataset is thus reducing as we climb in the strata.

Vegetation density and canopy models

For the 20 vegetation strata, we ran 20 binomial linear mixed models (*lmer*) using nightingale presence and absence as response variable, and the density of the strata as predictor. As the number of absence points was not equal for all presence points, we used a one-to-one ratio and ran the set of presences and absences 4000 times, randomly sampling one absence for each presence. Rounds of surveys and pairs of presences and absences were set as random factors. We used the estimates and standard errors of the models to calculate the 95% confidence interval for each stratum.

As a second step, and based on the previous *lmer*, we modeled the response curves of the first six layers and the canopy height using the function *sim* of the package ‘arm’ (Gelman et al. 2018) to get 1000 draws from the joint posterior distribution (*sim* applies flat priors), which were used to draw the trendline of the 4000 *lmer* models for the six strata. We used six different *lmer* models as the layers show a high correlation and could not be used in a single model.

As a complementary analysis, we conducted a principal component analysis (PCA) on the complete presence–absence dataset (i.e. all voxels between 0 and 20 m). We retained individual scores for the first five principal components, each with eigenvalues greater than 1, in accordance with the Kaiser criterion (Kaiser 1960). To assess their predictive value, we modeled 4000 randomly selected presence–absence pairs (at a 1:1 ratio) using a linear mixed-effects model (*lmer*), with nightingale presence/absence as the response variable and the PCA scores from components 1 to 5 as fixed predictors. Survey rounds and matched presence–absence pairs were included as random effects.

Habitat suitability models

Then, based on the outputs of the vegetation density models, we selected the five density layers showing a significant response to nightingale presence (in green in Fig. 1) and the canopy class layer to run a habitat suitability model: the ground layer (0–1 m; hereafter named R01), a sum from the

layers between 2 and 6 m (2–3; 3–4; 4–5; 5–6 m; hereafter named R26) and the canopy height layer (canopy). Pooling the variables for the layers 2–6 m enabled us to limit collinearity between the variables below $|<0.7|$, a reasonable value that enables their use in habitat suitability models (Dormann et al. 2013). Similarly to the previous analysis, these three layers have been processed with a moving window of 1.5 m to calculate the median vegetation density or canopy height for each pixel. Then, we used the full set of presences/absences to model the habitat suitability using the ‘biomod2’ package (Thuiller et al. 2024). This package is specially designed to model species distributions using different algorithms (Thuiller et al. 2009). In our case, we used a generalized boosted regressions (GBM) algorithm. As this algorithm is fine-tuned for species distribution models, we kept the original settings. We used a 100-times bootstrap procedure using 80% of the dataset to build a model and 20% to evaluate it. We evaluated the models using an internal function of the package to calculate true skills statistics (TSS: Allouche et al. 2006) and receiver operating curve (ROC: Hanley and Mcneil 1982), two metrics used to assess the quality of species distribution models. We then used these GBM models to project the potential habitat for the nightingales along the whole river at the scale of 1×1 m. Based on each metric, ‘biomod2’ calculates an ensemble forecasting model using the weights of the different runs according to their ROC or TSS score to build a final suitability map for each metric with each pixel containing a continuous value of suitability (from 0 = unsuitable to 1 = highly suitable). As both maps showed a high correlation, we used ROC only in further analysis (correlation of suitability map based on ROC and TSS > 0.9). ‘Biomod2’ also provides a threshold to separate suitable habitat from unsuitable based on a maximization of the ROC (or TSS) metric (set at 0.535 for ROC) based on ‘biomod2’ setting (Thuiller et al. 2024). In such a case, the new suitability maps were discarded from values below 0.535. We then used these new maps to calculate the amount of suitable habitat along the river for the nightingale. However, visual inspection of the outputs showed that the habitat was still overestimated by the HSM models (i.e. with the inclusion of fruit cultures in the maps). We decided to restrict the habitat maps based on the values of the fruit cultures in the model. To remove the bias of fruit cultures, we restricted the model on a step-by-step approach from the full habitat map with 100% of suitable habitat (or pixels), to 50, 25, 20, 10, and 5% of suitable habitat. We checked which threshold would remove 99% of the fruit cultures and kept it for the final suitability map. Finally, we extracted the variable importance value for the three variables (the ground layer: R01, the sum from the layers between 2 and 6 m: R26 and the canopy height class layer: canopy) of the models using the native *biomod2* function for the three predictors. The importance of the variables is calculated using variable permutations and comparing the outputs of a model with one variable permuted with the reference model. In our case, we ran the model three times, each run permuting one of the three variables and calculating a Pearson’s correlation

Figure 1. Estimates of vegetation density from LiDAR for presences points and absences points at 25 m (lines). Each stratum was modelled 4000 times; significant models (with 95% confidence intervals not crossing 0) are depicted by a green line. The dots represent the median. On the left side of the graph, the average height of nightingale observation is represented from min to max (dotted lines) and 2.5–97.5 quartiles (bold plain lines). The median is represented by a horizontal line. The black dots in the background show a LiDAR cloud of points of the river bank.

between the reference model and the permuted model. The importance of each of the variables is calculated as $1 - \text{correlation coefficient}$. In our case, we used three permutations. All the statistical analyses have been conducted in R ver. 4.3.3 (www.r-project.org).

Results

Description of the habitat

The bird monitoring led to the collection of 357 nightingale presence data, of which 347 were usable for further analysis. The birds were observed mostly in patches with trees and relatively high vegetation items. The distribution of the data is relatively homogeneous across the canopy values, with 71% of the presence data found in areas with woody vegetation up to 10 m tall. This percentage decreases to 53% for a height of 15 m and to 11% above 20 m (median 11.65 m, 25 and 75th percentiles: 6.36, 16.98, Table 1). Birds were recorded in vegetation patches from 2 m width to large forest patches (> 50 m) (Supporting information). Removing width values above 50 m that are not associated with river dams but are linked to nearby forest patches allows to focus solely on the vegetation corridors along the river. When excluding these values, birds were present in patches with a median vegetation width of 13 m, ranging from 9 to 20 m (25th and 75th percentiles).

Our results indicate that 11% of the birds could cope with very small vegetation patches, i.e. between 5 and 7 m width. Nightingales were found at an average height of 2.4 m (visual estimation in the field, $n = 253$, range = 0–8 m).

LiDAR data

The preference of the nightingale for dense, low vegetation layers but opened at the ground level is supported by our models, where nightingales showed a clear, strata-dependent preference regarding the density of vegetation (Fig. 1). In the lowest vegetation layer, between the ground and 1 m, nightingales preferred an open habitat with a vegetation density lower than average (Fig. 1–2, Table 1). The opposite was found in the low to middle vegetation layers, i.e. layers between 3–4, 4–5, and 5–6 m and to a lesser extent between 2–3 m, where nightingales prefer denser vegetation covers (Fig. 1–2, Table 1). Above 6 m, there appears to be no clear preference in terms of vegetation density. The probability of finding a bird also tends to increase with a high canopy cover, showing a preference for mature stands rather than young bushes (Fig. 2).

The correspondence analysis approach mainly corroborates the univariate single-layer approach, with components 1, 2, 3, and 4 showing significant differences between presence and absence points (Supporting information). Component 1, being mainly an indicator of high amounts of bare ground above bushes/trees, was significantly higher in presence than

Table 1. Mixed models outputs for the layers 1–20. The estimates and the confidences are used to build Fig. 1. ‘NB presences’ indicates the number of presence points used to build the model.

Voxel (height [m])	Estimate 25 m	SE 25 m	Confidence 2.5	Confidence 97.5	NB presence
0–1	-0.0368	0.0031	-0.0430	-0.0307	347
1–2	0.0174	0.0125	-0.0076	0.0425	336
2–3	0.031	0.015	0.001	0.060	334
3–4	0.046	0.019	0.009	0.084	326
4–5	0.047	0.022	0.002	0.092	322
5–6	0.066	0.027	0.013	0.120	302
6–7	0.055	0.028	-0.0001	0.110	291
7–8	0.047	0.030	-0.012	0.107	276
8–9	0.040	0.029	-0.018	0.097	263
9–10	0.044	0.033	-0.022	0.110	245
10–11	0.032	0.033	-0.034	0.098	236
11–12	0.024	0.032	-0.040	0.089	226
12–13	0.014	0.035	-0.056	0.083	214
13–14	-0.006	0.038	-0.083	0.071	201
14–15	0.046	0.038	-0.030	0.121	185
15–16	0.031	0.036	-0.041	0.102	172
16–17	0.015	0.042	-0.070	0.099	149
17–18	0.052	0.041	-0.031	0.134	120
18–19	0.069	0.055	-0.042	0.179	102
19–20	-0.007	0.062	-0.130	0.117	86

in absence points (0.39 ± 0.37 , z -value=10.67, p -value < 0.0001). Component 2, mainly indicating the presence of bushes and trees from 2 to 10 m was higher in presence versus absence points (0.25 ± 0.39 , z -value=6.24, p -value < 0.0001). Component 3 shows a slightly more complex pattern, with high vegetation density values from 2 to 6 m with large, dense trees between 16 and 20 m. Again, nightingale presence points had significantly higher component 3 values than absence points (0.34 ± 0.05 , z -value=6.60, p -value < 0.0001). Finally, the slight preference for component 4 was again associated with high-density bushes at low strata (2–34 m) with dense trees between 11 and 15 m (0.16 ± 0.59 , z -value=2.71, p -value=0.03).

Habitat suitability models

The GBM performed well with a median ROC of 0.84 and a TSS of 0.57 (25 to 75%: ROC 0.83–0.85; TSS 0.55–0.60; Supporting information). The importance of the variables showed a low importance of the canopy variable (0.3), in contrast to the ground layer R01 (0.44) and layer R26 (0.29) (Fig. 3). The internal density of the vegetation is more important than the height of the canopy. The total surface of the area covered by the LiDAR data represents 23'422'999 pixels of 1 m² (2342 ha). ROC and TSS suitability maps were highly correlated and showed very similar results (Spearman's rank correlation=0.99; Supporting information); only the suitability map based on ROC was kept for further analysis.

Figure 2. (A) Response curves of univariate models (4000 times each) for the strata 0–1 m in red, 1–2 m in violet, 2–3 m in blue, 3–4 m in green, 4–5 m in yellow. (B) Response curve of univariate models for the canopy cover. All the models are calculated presence/absences as random factors. Bold lines show the mean values.

Figure 3. Boxplots of the importance of the variables for the bio-mod2 models calculated as $1 - \text{the correlation coefficient}$. In this case, we used three permutations.

In this map, 16.0% (374 ha) were considered suitable for the nightingale according to the ensemble forecasting of 'bio-mod2' based on the ROC filtering threshold. However, this restriction was insufficient to remove some unfavorable habitats still considered by the model, like fruit cultures (Fig. 4). We used an additional filtering to restrict the model to the most suitable pixels and remove 99% of the fruit cultures, to provide an HSM closer to the actual distribution of the species along the river. Setting this new threshold corresponds to the quantile 50% (8% of the total surface of the LiDAR, 1678 ha) of the most suitable pixels and removed 99% of the inadequate habitat pixels in fruit cultures (Supporting information) and checked which step would remove 99% of the fruit cultures.

Discussion

High-resolution LiDAR data allowed us to comprehensively analyze the habitat use of the nightingale along the two longitudinal dams of a river corridor (80 km each, 160 km in total). On a small scale and in terms of vegetation height, we see a preference for dense vegetation between 3 and 6 m in height (confirmed by the single-layer approach and PC 3 and 4), above a ground layer (0–1 m) composed of sparse vegetation (confirmed by single layer approach and PC1). These results are consistent with previous field studies on the habitat use of the nightingale (Stuttard and Williamson 1971, Wilson et al. 2005, Holt et al. 2012) and demonstrated that LiDAR data can provide good habitat density information

over very large areas to understand species–habitat relationships of endangered birds, such as the nightingale. Even if, in our case, habitat suitability models based on LiDAR data show a broader habitat than that used by the birds, these data can easily be refined to precisely target areas in need of conservation measures.

Nightingales need very specific and complementary habitats to breed and forage (Wilson et al. 2005). As ground foragers, they rely on high amounts of bare ground combined with sparse ground vegetation (Schaub et al. 2010). These patches of bare ground improve birds' maneuverability, and increase food detection and its accessibility. Open habitat during foraging also helps to reduce the risk of predation, as predators are more visible and can be spotted more quickly. This risk can be reduced even more by foraging in sheltered and relatively hidden areas. This was demonstrated by the dense vegetation layer, preferred by nightingales at heights of 3–6 m in our study, as also shown by Wilson et al. (2005). A dense shrub layer beneath a tall canopy, highlighted by the significant principal component 3 effect, can serve multiple functions for a breeding bird like the nightingale. It provides a sheltered spot for singing while also offering a secure hiding place for nesting and protecting vulnerable nestlings. The positive correlation with canopy cover indicates that nightingales in our study are mainly found in forest-like structures with a dense shrub cover close to the ground but that they avoid shrub-only structures, contrary to Wilson et al. (2005). However, this discrepancy between the two regions rather indicates that similar fine-scaled ecological niches can be found in different habitats and should not be seen as a weakness of the LiDAR approach, especially as the study of Wilson et al. was close to the edge of the distribution range for the species, which can result in changes in habitat use as shown for the western capercaillie (Braunisch et al. 2008).

Our results, which are based on a large-scale remote sensing approach, are consistent with the fine-scale field study by Wilson et al. (2005). It seems particularly remarkable that the high-resolution LiDAR was capable of correctly describing a wide variety of vegetation layers and thus the density information important for the nightingale. The acquisition of this 3D information is essential to define the habitat requirements of the birds, and detailed 3D vegetation density can only be achieved with high-resolution LiDAR datasets (Jakubowski et al. 2013, Bakx et al. 2019). Leveraging these density data, which are made accessible by LiDAR across large-scale and continuous landscapes, enables the implementation of targeted conservation strategies in areas where detailed structural criteria are absent. In such context, LiDAR and its derived metrics can help to define ecosystems and preferred habitats of target species and ultimately be an important tool for conservation planning.

Despite its promising use for habitat description, it is important to remember that LiDAR will cover only vegetation structures. For numerous species, the structure of the vegetation is as important as its composition, and LiDAR data will omit some specific needs for specialist species. Although identifying the tree and bush assemblages in forests

using LiDAR appears to be achievable (Allen et al. 2023), precisely identifying each species is still a challenge. This knowledge has, however, a great impact on the presence of bird species, i.e. for species that feed on berries or need coniferous species. Similarly, it is not yet possible to assess the floral composition of the herbaceous layer with LiDAR data, as non-woody vegetation will return laser signals poorly. Likewise, even if hyperspectral methods are showing promising results (Moudry et al. 2023), it is challenging to get good proxies for the amount of lying or standing dead wood. These structural elements are, however, highly important for forest ecosystems, where they are used as biodiversity indicators (Lassauce et al. 2011, Bouvet et al. 2016, Oettel and Lapin 2021). The actual limitation of LiDAR technology in identifying these objects shows the need to combine this method with other remote sensing approaches (like infrared or hyperspectral images to calculate indexes like NDVI) and maximize the knowledge gain to understand species habitat.

Despite the very accurate description of the habitat used by nightingales, we still need to quantify the available habitat surface in order to target conservation areas or promote new ones. Whereas HSMs are widely used at coarser scales to identify habitat suitability for birds (i.e. Theux et al. 2022, with fine-scale below 25 m pixels), identification of suitable habitats remains rare for birds (Segal et al. 2021). At

such small scales, the usual topo-climatic variables used to model species distribution are not helpful, and in our case, we used only variables from the LiDAR data. With this modeling process, we were able to show that 16% of the total surface of the riverbanks in the actual management scheme shows potentially interesting habitat for the nightingales, but this percentage needs to be lowered as probably only 50% of this 16% surface is actually favorable for the nightingale. The threshold provided by the ROC and TSS metrics is not restrictive enough, mainly due to the use of structural and density variables only (in HSM models, climatic or satellite images are also used to fully depict the habitat of a given species not available for our study at 1 m resolution), indicating some intensively managed fruit cultures as favorable even though they were never occupied by the birds (Fig. 4). Restricting the surface to the most favorable pixels, however, provides more relevant results and a useful suitability map showing less than 168 ha of scattered favorable habitat along the 160 km of riverbanks. This remaining favorable habitat is very restricted, but the potential of the river for the nightingale population is 10 times higher, as shown by monitorings from the 1980s, where the number of birds was multiplied by 10 compared to actual densities (Arlettaz and Posse, unpubl.). Moreover, because an area of 1 m² pixel is not sufficient for a bird to breed, only favorable surfaces of

Figure 4. Example of an area with fruit cultures (in yellow and orange) shown as potential habitat. The vegetation on one side of the riverbank is very scattered and provides only a small surface of suitable habitat, while the other side shows larger vegetation patches. The scale of colors indicates the different suitability levels from 100% (full model) to 5% of the most suitable pixels. Restricting the model to 50% of the most suitable pixels will remove 99% of the inadequate structures like fruit cultures (visible in yellow in the right and lower part of the map).

the size of a nightingale territory ($\sim 5000 \text{ m}^2$; von Blotzheim and Bauer 1988) should be considered. However, due to the complex shape of the riverbanks, the calculation of these potential territories is challenging. The small width of the forest patches along the river makes it difficult to estimate territories accurately because they cannot be resumed by circles. To conduct a proper analysis of territories (and not individual sightings), one should use a multiscale analysis with different radii from a minimum of 40 m, and up to 100 m to compare different surfaces of potential territories. However, again, the topography of the river banks makes this analysis impossible to conduct as most of the surface with a given radius would be out of the LiDAR data. A visual inspection of the data reveals that areas with low habitat suitability typically exhibit a scattered distribution of suitable habitats (i.e. Fig 4). This pattern is very useful to point out regions where conservation measures should be implemented, i.e. to enhance the surface and the quality of these scattered habitats.

Remote sensing technologies should be combined with detailed field studies to identify species' fine-scale habitat structures over large areas and to propose efficient conservation planning. As it is unlikely that the critical resources of some species can be quantified using remote sensing technologies only, the inclusion of variables, i.e. taking into account vegetation taxa, might be useful.

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Author contributions

Jean-Nicolas Pradervand: Conceptualization (lead); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (lead); Investigation (equal); Methodology (lead); Project administration (lead); Software (equal); Supervision (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review and editing (lead). **Florian Zellweger:** Conceptualization (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Methodology (equal); Software (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Jérémy Gremion:** Data curation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Aristide Parisod:** Data curation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Bertrand Posse:** Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Emmanuel Revaz:** Data curation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Alain Jacot:** Conceptualization (lead); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (lead); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review and editing (lead).

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Data availability statement

Data are available from the Zenodo Digital Repository: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15409534> (Pradervand et al. 2025).

Supporting information

The Supporting information associated with this article is available with the online version.

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